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THE CENTENNIAL OF THE HAGUE ACADEMY AND OUR REGION

This paper presents the slightly extended content of a presentation delivered at the 18th Regional Private International Law Conference in Niš, which traces the historical presence of The Hague Academy of International Law in the consciousness of the South Slavs region, particularly during the period from 1918-1991 when the region existed as the State of Yugoslavia. The paper explores how diplomats and scholars in this newly formed State, emerging from the aftermath of World War I, enthusiastically embraced and participated in the establishment and activities of The Hague Academy. The Academy aimed at promoting and facilitating "a thorough and impartial examination of the problems arising from international juridical relations." The early relationship was marked by a shared trust in international law as an instrument for peacebuilding. Subsequent events reveal a pattern of interactions with the developing branches of Public and Private International Law becoming pivotal for long-lasting peace in Europe. During this period, a majority of international law professors from the region attended The Hague Academy, contributing not only as attendees but also as professors and researchers. The relationship reached a culmination during the breakup of Yugoslavia, a defining moment that unexpectedly amplified the activities of the Academy. This shift offered new topics for discussion and research, including secession and dissolution, recognition of new States, division of property, debts and archives, international criminal courts and tribunals and more.

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The presentation draws on the writings of several Yugoslav scholars on The Hague Academy throughout the years, books published during the 75th and 100th jubilee of The Hague Academy, and research from Recueil des cours.

Keywords: *The Hague Academy of International Law, Yugoslavia, Private International Law.*

1. Introduction

Today, I would like to discuss The Hague Academy of International Law. While it may not be considered a traditional international organisation -- it was established as a Dutch not-for-profit foundation¹ -- its international purpose and structure are evident. In every respect, be it its administration or the continuously evolving composition of its faculty and attendees, it embodies an international essence and demonstrates meticulous organization. The auditorium of The Hague Academy sees representation from more than one hundred countries every year, as students from around the world gather to listen to The Hague lectures.²

The idea for the Academy's organization can be traced back to the Second Hague Peace Conference of 1907. It is attributed to the German jurist, Ludwig von Bar.³ He envisioned the Academy as an advisory body comprising eminent legal scholars who would offer guidance to States in arbitration cases.⁴ On 2 September 1912, a Consultative Committee consisting of ten members from the Institute for International Law, including individuals like Tobias Asser, Ludwig Von Bar, Louis Renault and the Yugoslav ambassador in Paris, Milenko Vesnić, recommended the establishment of an academy aimed at promoting and facilitating "a thorough and impartial examination of the problems arising from international juridical relations."⁵ Vesnić also

¹ The Foundation named The Hague Academy of International Law was established by notarial deed on 27 January 1914 with its headquarters in the municipality of the Hague. Art. 1 of the Statutes of the Foundation, <https://www.hagueacademy.nl/statutes/>.

² Thouvenin, J-M, *Préface*, 100e Anniversaire Académie de droit international de La Haye/100th Anniversary The Hague Academy of International Law 1923-2023 (hereinafter : 100e anniversaire), (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, pp. 11-12.

³ Joor, J, *The Hague Academy from a Historical Perspective*, 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, p. 15.

⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 22.

⁵ Dupuis, R. J, *Livre jubilee/Jubilee Book 1923-1973*, Leiden: The Hague Academy of International Law, 1973, p. 27. Joor, op.cit., p. 26. This wording was included in the original

participated in the five sessions of the Consultative Committee that drafted the Statutes of the Academy in January 1914.⁶

Tobias Asser is acknowledged as the Academy's founding figure, not only for his involvement in this initiative but also because he donated a portion of the Nobel Peace Prize money for the Academy's founding. Sadly, he didn't live to see his vision for the Academy realized, as he passed away in 1913.⁷ The inaugural ceremony, originally scheduled for 1 October 1914, was postponed due to the outbreak of the First World War, and the first group of students didn't attend the lectures until 1923.

How many individuals in this room have had the opportunity to attend The Hague Academy at least once during their lifetime? Please show your hands. I trusted that a significant number of you would, as this institution is and has always been a hothouse for nurturing future international law scholars.

2. Back to the beginnings: turning the yellowed pages of Arhiv and Anali

The Hague Academy released a commemorative book to mark its 100th anniversary which I received as a gift this summer. I used this book as a reference while preparing today's presentation. However, I believed it would be interesting to cross-reference the information by consulting local law journals for additional insights into the Academy's history and activities from a local perspective.

2.1. Curatorium

Let's explore the pages of the Archive for Social and Legal Sciences and Annales, the publications of the Faculty of Law at the University of Belgrade. In the 1930 issue, professor Živojin Perić writes about The Hague Academy of International Law. He informs us that this educational institution was established in 1921 with support from the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace and holds the status of a university.⁸ Lectures are conducted

statutes of the Foundation. The statutes were changed in 2018, so that now this part of Article 2 reads: "with the aim of promoting in-depth scientific research on issues relating to international legal relationships..." Art. 2 of the Statutes of the Foundation, <https://www.hagueacademy.nl/statutes/>.

⁶Dupuis, *op.cit.*, p. 28.

⁷Daudet, Y, *Propos conclusifs, l'Academie demain?*, 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, p. 200.

⁸The purpose of the Foundation is to be a centre for the advanced study of and research

annually in July and August by professors from both Dutch and international backgrounds, selected for each session by the Academy's Curatorium, a body comprising twelve distinguished jurists specializing in international law. Among its members is D. Anzilotti, the president of the recently established Permanent Court of International Justice and a professor at the University of Rome. The Curatorium is responsible for overseeing the Academy's academic direction, including the selection of scholars and topics for instruction.⁹ According to the former Dutch Minister of Foreign Affairs and President of the Academy's Administrative Board, the Curatorium has consistently been the driving force and the heart of the Academy.¹⁰

In the present day, the Academy's Statute stipulates that the Curatorium must consist of a minimum of seven members and no more than nineteen. Furthermore, it specifies that there can be no more than one representative from the same country serving on the Curatorium simultaneously.¹¹ This group of academics from around the world convenes biannually to establish the curriculum and select lecturers well in advance of the courses. On certain occasions, invitations are issued as early as four or five years in advance of the summer course.

Throughout the century of the Academy's existence, only ten individuals have held the position of president of the Curatorium. These notable figures include Boutros-Ghali, a former UN Secretary-General, Nicolas Valticos, who served as a judge at the European Court of Human Rights, and Robert Ago, a judge at the International Court of Justice. The current president of the Curatorium, in office since 2017, is Yves Daudet, an emeritus professor at Paris I University Pantheon-Sorbonne.¹²

It is worth noting that from 1923 to 2022, there were only eight female members of the Curatorium in comparison to ninety male members. The appointment of the first women did not occur until as late as 2005. Presently, out of the nineteen current Curatorium members, five are women.¹³

on international public and private law and related sciences, with the aim of promoting in depth scientific research on issues relating to international legal relationships by conducting educational and research activities and any other activity that could contribute towards achieving this objective. Art. 2 of the Statutes of the Foundation, <https://www.hagueacademy.nl/statutes/>.

⁹ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 27.

¹⁰ Bot, B, *A profound Impact on my Life*, 100e anniversaire, 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, p. 146.

¹¹ Art. 6 of the Statute, <https://www.hagueacademy.nl/statutes/>.

¹² 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, Annexes, p. 204.

¹³ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 81.

This gender imbalance has led to the characterization of the Curatorium as a “men’s club”.¹⁴

It is also worth noting that the Academy does not have and has never had the status of a university.¹⁵ The original plans for its establishment did assume a permanent university, but these were abandoned early on for an institution which would only offer courses during the summer months, to be taught by a changing group of international experts.¹⁶

2.2. The Secretary-General

An important figure of The Hague Academy is its Secretary-General. According to Article 8 of the Academy’s Statutes, the Curatorium appoints the Secretary-General through a secret ballot for a six-year term. The Secretary-General holds responsibility for scientific and educational matters, operating under the authority of the Curatorium. Since the establishment of the Academy, there have been only nine individuals who have held the position of Secretary-General. Traditionally, the Secretary-General has been a French citizen, with only two exceptions. Notably, Genevieve Bastid-Burdeau, who served as Secretary-General from 1999 to 2004, was the sole woman to have held this position.¹⁷ Since 2017, the position of Secretary-General is held by Professor Jean-Marc Thouvenin, who is a professor of Public International Law at the Paris Nanterre University.

2.3. The Academy Building

Professor Perić highlights that the Academy is housed within the iconic Peace Palace (Palais de la Paix), which is also the seat of the Permanent Court of Arbitration and the Permanent Court of International Justice.¹⁸ However, in 1933, a separate academy building with an auditorium was put in use, serving the Academy and housing the Library’s book depot for the subsequent

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ Daudet, *op.cit.*, p. 198.

¹⁶ Joor, *op.cit.*, 24.

¹⁷ It has been pointed out that the position of Secretary-General of the Hague Conference for Private International Law has never been held by a woman. Keyes, M, *Women in Private International Law*, Research Handbook on Feminist Engagement with International Law, (eds. S. Harris Rimmer, K. Ogg), Camberley and Northampton: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2019, p. 117.

¹⁸ Perić, Ž, *Association des auditeurs et anciens auditeurs de l’Académie de Droit international de la Haye*, A.A.A. Bulletin No. 7, Novembre 1929, Arhiv za pravne i društvene nauke, knjiga trideset sedma, 1930, p. 241. The Permanent Court of Arbitration was founded by the Convention on Pacific Settlement of International Disputes 1899, and the Permanent Court of International Justice was established by the Covenant of the League of Nations of 28 June 1919.

seventy years.¹⁹ In 2005, both the book depot and the Academy building were demolished, making way for the construction of a new modern, and spacious Library and Academy building, which was completed and opened in 2007.

The Hague Conference on Private International Law played an important role in instigating this construction project. The conferences and meetings organized by the Hague Conference, taking place every four years and attended by the representatives of member states as well as non-governmental organizations, were frequently held in the Academy building. As the Hague Conference's membership grew over the years, the original Academy building could no longer provide adequate accommodations. Consequently, A.V.M. Struycken, a Dutch professor of Private International Law and one of the Conferences' delegates, proposed the renovation of the building. It is worth noting that the 22th Diplomatic Session of the Hague Conference, during which the Judgments Convention was adopted, took place in the Academy's building.

2.4. The Attendees

Professor Perić then discusses the audience of the Academy, which mainly comprises graduate students and experienced law professionals, particularly those with "established social standing". The Academy is specially intended for civil servants working in foreign ministries and legal practitioners.²⁰ In 1929, there were 433 attendees including 93 females.²¹

In its 100 years of existence, the Academy has had tens of thousands of attendees following its summer courses. Between 1992 and 1998, the number of participants at The Hague Academy declined from 600 to slightly over 500. However, starting in 2009, the participant count began to increase once more and consistently surpasses 650. Notably, the number of participants in Public Law courses consistently exceeded the number of participants in

¹⁹ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 44.

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ Thirty-three countries were represented, twenty-one from Europe, nine from Americas, two from Asia and one from Africa. The composition was as follows: 64 attendees from Germany, 41 from Poland, 26 from the US, 26 from Italy, 19 from France, 14 from the UK, 9 from Egypt, 9 from Romania, 8 from China, 8 from Greece, 8 from Hungary, 6 from Belgium, 6 from Switzerland, 4 from Chile, 4 from Cuba, 3 from Austria, 3 from Russia, two from Free city of Dancig, 2 from British Indies, 2 from Sweden, 2 from the Czech Republic and one attendee per the following countries: Albania, Argentina, Bulgaria, Canada, Columbia, Costa Rica, Denmark, Spain, Mexico, Uruguay and Yugoslavia. Other attendees (157 of them) came from the Netherlands. Perić, *op.cit.*, p. 242.

Private Law courses.²² The number of participants in the Private Law sessions remained consistently around 250.²³

In 2021, as a response to the pandemic, all courses were conducted online. To address the challenge of accommodating participants from various international time zones, two broadcasts were scheduled per day. This innovative approach allowed for an unprecedented participation of approximately 1200 attendees.²⁴

This summer (2023), the Academy was attended by 348 attendees in public international law and 315 attendees in Private International Law. Additionally, 114 online attendees were registered for the former and 69 for the latter, which makes a total of 462 public and 384 private international law students.

In 1923, there were 35 women among the attendees, constituting approximately 10% of the total. By 1929, when Professor Perić wrote his note, the percentage of female participants had increased to 21%. Remarkably, in 2019 and 2020 female participants outnumbered their male counterparts, becoming the majority in both summer and winter courses. The first female from Yugoslavia to attend the academy was Anka Gođevac. She additionally achieved the distinction of becoming the first woman to earn PhD in international law in Yugoslavia.²⁵

Winter courses were introduced in 2019.²⁶ They closely follow the structure and format of the Summer courses. However, one notable difference is that there is no distinct period dedicated to public and private law in the Winter courses.²⁷ Public international law lectures are somewhat more prominent compared to private law lectures.²⁸

²² Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 79.

²³ *Ibid.*, p. 69.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 85. Legerman, M, *The Evolution of the Secretariat of the Academy*, 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, p. 182.

²⁵ Djajić, S, *Standing Alone but Standing Tall: A Female Perspective of International Law from the Interwar Yugoslavia*, Legal Issues of International Law from a Gender Perspective, Gender Perspectives in Law (Vol. 3), (eds. I. Krstić, M. Evola, M.I. Ribes Moreno), New York: Springer, 2023, Cham. pp. 200-224.

²⁶ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 81.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 85.

²⁸ Nishitani, Y, *The Recueil des cours and Private International Law*, General Part and Family Law, 100e anniversaire, 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, p. 124.

2.5. Participation of Yugoslav Students

In his brief note, Professor Perić advocates for increased participation of Yugoslav lawyers in the Academy, specifically encouraging civil servants from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. He believes that this would bring a two-fold advantage to the country: attendees would enhance their legal knowledge while establishing connections that would serve the cause of peace and their country's interests.

He notes that the sole attendee from Yugoslavia that year was V. Pavlaković, an attaché at the Yugoslav consulate in the Hague. Over the first seven years of the Academy's operation, there was only one other attendee from Yugoslavia, Stevan Ćirković, an attaché at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, who received a scholarship from Carnegie in 1926.²⁹ Anka Gođevac attended the Academy in 1930. In 1933, following the publication of professor Perić's note, Ilija Pržić, a future professor of Public International Law at Belgrade University, received a scholarship from Yugoslav Rotary club to attend the Academy.³⁰

Several post-war attendees who wrote about the Academy in domestic legal periodicals include Smilja Avramov,³¹ Vojin Dimitrijević,³² Stevan Đorđević,³³ Milenko Kreća,³⁴ Budislav Vukas,³⁵ and Momir Milojević.³⁶ In

²⁹ Đajić, S., Ćirković, S, (1899-1991) – *Biografija jednog međunarodnog pravnika*, Srpski godišnjak za međunarodno pravo (3. izdanje), (ed. D. Dimitrijević), Beograd: Srpsko udruženje za međunarodno pravo, 2023, pp. 13-26.

³⁰ Pržić, I, *Haška akademija za međunarodno pravo*, Arhiv za pravne i društvene nauke, 45, 1934, p. 177.

³¹ Avramov, S, *Dvadeset i četvrti kurs na Haškoj akademiji za međunarodno pravo*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Beogradu (B), 2 (3–4), 1953, pp. 509–512

³² Dimitrijević, V, *Predavanja na Haškoj akademiji za međunarodno pravo u toku 1963*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Beogradu (B), 11 (3–4), 1963, p. 574.

³³ Đorđević, S, *Haška akademija za međunarodno pravo u 1964 i plan rada za 1965*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Beogradu (B), 12 (4), 1964, pp. 495–497. Đorđević, S, *Haška Akademija za međunarodno pravo u 1968. godini*, (B), 16 (2), 1968, pp. 294–295. Stevan Đorđević participated in the Center for Scientific Research of the Hague Academy in 1962 and 1966. Trkulja, J, *Sećanja*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Beogradu, 69 (1), p. 294.

³⁴ Kreća, M, *Letnji kurs Haške akademije za međunarodno pravo u 1976. godini*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Beogradu (B), 24 (6), 1976, pp. 765–770.

³⁵ Vukas, B, *Rad Centra za studije i istraživanje međunarodnog prava i međunarodnih odnosa Haške akademije za međunarodno pravo u 1967. godini*, Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta u Zagrebu, 18 (1), 1968, pp. 102-108. Vukas, B, *Haška akademija za međunarodno pravo u 1968. godini*, Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta u Zagrebu, 19 (1), 1969, p. 107.

³⁶ Milojević, M, *Haška akademija za međunarodno pravo u 1968. godini*, Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Beogradu (B), 17 (3–4), 1969, pp. 503–505.

1964, S. Đorđević noted that the Academy had held courses annually since 1923, except for the interruption from 1940-1946.

Ms Chloe Bachelor from the Secretariat of the Hague Academy compiled the following statistics regarding the participation of scholars from the Socialist Republic of Yugoslavia in the summer programs of The Hague Academy throughout the years.

Yugoslav attendees 1958 – 1991:

	Year	Public	Private
1.	1952		4
2.	1953		9
3.	1954		11
4.	1955		13
5.	1956		13
6.	1957		8
7.	1958	6	6
8.	1959	7	5
9.	1960	6	4
10.	1961	7	2
11.	1962	5	3
12.	1963	13	2
13.	1964	7	3
14.	1965	3	3
15.	1966	5	4
16.	1967	5	3
17.	1968	6	2
18.	1969	3	5
19.	1970	7	3
20.	1971	2	3
21.	1972	2	0
22.	1973	2	0
23.	1974	3	2
24.	1975	4	4
25.	1976	5	3
26.	1977	5	1
27.	1978	4	8
28.	1979	3	2
29.	1980	5	2
30.	1981	6	7
31.	1982	5	4
32.	1983	3	2
33.	1984	2	6
34.	1985	2	0
35.	1986	6	5
36.	1987	3	5
37.	1988	0	4
38.	1989	4	4
39.	1990	7	6
40.	1991	4	3

Compiled by: Chloé Batchelor <c.batchelor@hagueacademy.nl>

Total participants: 331 (average per year: 8.27)

Total Public participants: 157 (average per year: 3.9)

Total Private: 116 (average per year: 2.9)

Notably, between 1952 and 1991, the total number of participants amounted to 331. Out of those 116 attended the courses in Private International Law. It is important to note that no data is accessible for the years preceding the Second World War nor for the years 1947-1951. This can be compared with the data for the period since 2010 available at The Hague Academy website:³⁷

Attendees of the Summer Courses (since 2010)

	Public International Law	Private International Law
Croatia	16	10
Serbia (including Kosovo)	11+3	10
North Macedonia	6	5
Slovenia	7	2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	5	2
Montenegro	1	0

Total participants: 78 (average per year: 5.57)

Total Public participants: 46 (average per year: 3.28)

Total Private: 29 (average per year: 2.,07)

These numbers show that, compared to the Yugoslav period, the number of student participants from the region has slightly declined in recent years.

I'd also like to provide an explanation for why the recording of data for Public and Private International Law was separated, commencing in the year 1958.

In the inaugural year of the Academy, 1923, the curriculum predominantly focused on public international law. It encompassed a blend of lecture series dedicated to the fundamental principles of international law, as well as discussions on current and emerging topics.³⁸ In the following year, general courses in Private International Law were introduced, offering insights into both the civil law system, taught by A. Pillet and the common law system, instructed by H. Bellot, in the two sessions. This development was succeeded by a series of courses devoted to exposition of national conceptions of Private International Law from various countries. Those lectures included W. Simons from Germany (1926), G. Diena from Italy (1927), G. Streit from Greece (1927), A. Kuhn from the USA (1928), J. Péritch from Yugoslavia (1929),

³⁷ Nationalities of the Attendees of the Summer Courses (since 2010), <https://www.hagueacademy.nl/represented-nationalities-summer-courses/>.

³⁸ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 36.

J. Trias de Bes from Spain (1930), S. Daneff from Bulgaria (1930), A. Makarov from Russia (1931), F. Pontes de Miranda from Brasil (1932), J. Sulkowski from Poland (1932) and E. Fabre-Surveyer from Canada (1935).³⁹

Subsequently, the focus shifted from a national approach to a regional and universal perspective on private international law.⁴⁰ In the early days of the Academy, it was not uncommon for lectures to encompass both fields, with notable lectures such as Rolin, Diena, Nolde, Fedozzi, and Niboyet.⁴¹

In 1958, a strict division of courses was introduced, with the first period dedicated to private international law and the second to public international law.⁴² The inaugural General Course in Private International Law, taught by B.A. Wortley, took place in 1958.⁴³ This arrangement remained in place until 2011 when the order was reversed, and public international law lectures were scheduled prior to private international law lectures.⁴⁴

However, even after this division, some scholars continued to interweave both fields in their lectures, as they regarded private international law as an integral part of public international law.⁴⁵ The demarcation between these two branches of law often remained ambiguous.⁴⁶ Additionally, there were specific subjects that necessitated examination from both perspectives, such as sovereign immunity, reciprocity, the rights of aliens, intellectual property protection and various other topics.⁴⁷

2.5.1. Alumni Association

In professor Perić's note regarding The Hague Academy, it was mentioned that there existed an Alumni Association which played an active role in coordinating social activities for the Academy's attendees during their stay in The Hague. This served to bring them together and foster friendships.⁴⁸ In

³⁹ Vitta, E, *Cours Général de droit international privé*, Recueil des cours, 162, 1979, p. 191 fn. 1.

⁴⁰ Nishitani, *op.cit.*, p. 120.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, p. 124.

⁴² Joor, *op.cit.*, 38.

⁴³ *Ibid.*, p. 55. Nishitani, *op.cit.*, p. 116, 118.

⁴⁴ Joor, *op.cit.*, 81.

⁴⁵ Nishitani, *op.cit.*, p. 125.

⁴⁶ Cordero-Moss, G, *The Recueil des Cours and Private International law, Business Law and Arbitration*, 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, p. 133.

⁴⁷ Nishitani, *op.cit.*, p. 125.

⁴⁸ Association des Auditeurs et Anciens Auditeurs de l'Académie de Droit international de La Haye/Association of Attendees and Alumni of the Hague Academy of International Law,

1933, Dr. Ilija Pržić was elected as one of five members on the board of the Alumni Association. The AAA (Alumni Association of the Academy) operated as an international network and was partly structured into national groups.

In 1962, Professor Borko Nikolajević,⁴⁹ who served as the president of the Yugoslav group of the global AAA, organized a congress for this organization in Dubrovnik.⁵⁰ One of the notable contributions of the Association was the publication of a yearbook, nowadays known as the Hague Yearbook of International Law.⁵¹ The Association was officially disbanded in 2017.⁵²

2.5.2. Diploma of the Academy

The famous diploma exam was introduced in 1949.⁵³ Obtaining the Diploma from the Academy remains a difficult task. Among the Yugoslav and the successor States candidates, only two succeeded in making it to the finish line: Željko Matić from the Zagreb Faculty of Law in 1960 and Andrijana Mišović from the Belgrade Faculty of Law in 2016.⁵⁴

2.5.3. Professors

More than thousand scholars, judges and diplomats taught at The Hague Academy. Their lectures have been compiled from year one into a remarkable collection, a veritable “green wall”⁵⁵, which is a unique monument⁵⁶ comprising more than 430 volumes of *Recueil des cours*.

It is noteworthy that, much like the Curatorium, the initial teaching faculty at the Academy consisted solely of men. The participation of female lecturers has historically been limited and has only started to see an increase in recent decades.⁵⁷

often denominated by the acronym AAA. Perić, *op.cit.*, p. 242.

⁴⁹ Professor of International Commercial Law at the Belgrade Faculty of Law, co-author with professor Bartoš of the book *Legal Status of Aliens*. Bartoš, M., Nikolajević, B, *Pravni položaj stranaca (savremena shvatanja međunarodne prakse u FNRJ)*, Beograd: Naučna knjiga, 1951.

⁵⁰ Radojković, M, *In memoriam: Dr Borko Nikolajević (1913-1964)*, *Anali Pravnog fakulteta u Beogradu*, 12 (1), 1964, p. 140.

⁵¹ *Annuaire de l'Association des Auditeurs et Anciens Auditeurs de l'Académie de Droit International de La Haye* = *Annual of the Association of Attenders and Alumni of the Hague Academy of International Law*, in 1988 renamed to: *Hague Yearbook of International Law*.

⁵² Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 77.

⁵³ *Ibid.*, p. 58.

⁵⁴ Awarded Diplomas since 1950, <https://www.hagueacademy.nl/awarded-diplomas/>.

⁵⁵ Thouvenin, *op.cit.*, p. 11.

⁵⁶ Kolb, R, *Recueil des cours*, 100e anniversaire, (ed. S. Cartier), The Hague: The Hague Academy of International Law, 2023, p. 95.

⁵⁷ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 81.

2.5.4. *Scholars from the former Yugoslavia*

Scholars from the former Yugoslavia and the succession States have occasionally been invited to serve as lecturers. Milovan Milovanović, professor of the Belgrade Faculty of Law, one of the leading Serbian jurists, and prime minister of Serbia,⁵⁸ was asked to deliver a course at the Academy in the early stages of its establishment⁵⁹ but did not live to see it fully realized.⁶⁰ During the era of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, four distinguished professors had the privilege of addressing attendees from the Academy lectern: professor Živojin Perić from the Belgrade University Faculty of Law delivered a special course in Private International Law in 1929.⁶¹ Subsequently, Professor Milorad Stražnjicki from the Zagreb University, also presented a special course on Private International Law.⁶² They were followed by Juraj Andrassy, who delivered a special course on Public International Law in 1937,⁶³ and Đorđe Tasić, who presented a special course on Public International Law in 1938.⁶⁴ Finally, professor Stražnjicki was invited back to teach another special course on Public International Law in 1939.⁶⁵

During the period of Socialist Yugoslavia, five professors lectured at the Academy: Professor Juraj Andrassy, presented a special course in Public International Law,⁶⁶ professor Milan Bartoš, offered a special course in Public International Law,⁶⁷ Professor Natko Katičić, taught a special course in

⁵⁸ Milovanović was educated in Belgrade and in Paris. He was the first Serb to take the degree of Doctor of Law in Paris and received a gold medal for his doctoral thesis. He represented Serbia at the 1907 Hague Peace Conference and was appointed a member of the Permanent Court of Arbitration thereafter. *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, 1922, p. 946.

⁵⁹ Dupuis, *op.cit.*, p. 26.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 26.

⁶¹ Péritch, J, *Conception du droit international privé d'après la doctrine et la pratique en Yougoslavie*, Recueil des cours, 28, 1929. Péritch studied law in Paris from 1888-1891.

⁶² Straznicky, M, *Les Conférences de droit international privé depuis la fin de la guerre mondiale*, Recueil des cours, 44, 1933. Straznicky received his doctorate in law at the University of Zagreb, but studied law also in Vienna, Berlin and Leipzig. He abandoned his professorship in 1929 to pursue a career in diplomacy.

⁶³ Andrassy, G, *La souveraineté et la Société des Nations*, Recueil des cours, 61, 1937. Andrassy received his doctorate in law at the University of Zagreb.

⁶⁴ Tassitch, G, *La conscience juridique internationale*, Recueil des cours, 65, 1938. Tassitch was professor of law at the University of Belgrade.

⁶⁵ Straznicky, M, *Jurisprudence de la Cour suprême de plébiscite du bassin de la Sarre*, Recueil des cours, 69, 1939.

⁶⁶ Andrassy, J, *Les relations internationales de voisinage*, Recueil des cours, 79, 1951.

⁶⁷ Bartoš, M, *Le statut des missions spéciales de la diplomatie ad hoc*, Recueil des cours, 108,

Private International Law,⁶⁸ Dr. Milan Šahović, delivered two special courses in Public International Law,⁶⁹ and Đuro Ninčić, provided a special course in Public International Law.⁷⁰

Following the dissolution of Yugoslavia, two Croatian professors, Degan⁷¹ and Vukas⁷² taught special courses in Public International Law. In 2023 a Serbian professor, Maja Stanivuković, delivered a special course in Private International Law.⁷³

For reference, Brill, the publisher of *Recueil des cours*, provides a list of authors that can be used as a search tool. All authors of Collected Courses, over one thousand, are listed in a separate entry at the website of Brill.⁷⁴ *Recueil des cours* contains a bibliographical note on each author.

2.5.5. The format of general courses

It is worth noting that no professor from the region had the opportunity to teach the prestigious general course of The Hague Academy,⁷⁵ whether in private or in public international law.

The General Course format evolved into a significant platform for the discussion of methodological and doctrinal issues,⁷⁶ where renowned professors exchanged their views. From a common law perspective, notable fig-

1963. Bartoš obtained his doctor of law diploma in Paris in 1927. He was professor at the Belgrade University and a diplomat. He was a member of the Permanent Court of Arbitration and the International Law Commission.

⁶⁸ Katičić, N, *Le droit international privé de la Yougoslavie dans le domaine des rapports familiaux et successoraux*, Recueil des cours, 131, 1970. Katičić studied law at the University of Zagreb and University of Vienna.

⁶⁹ Šahović, M, *Codification des principes du droit international des relations amicales et de la coopération entre les Etats*, Recueil des cours, 137, 1972. Šahović, M, *Rapports entre facteurs matériels et facteurs formels dans la formation du droit international*, Recueil des cours, 199, 1986. Šahović received his doctorate in law at the University of Belgrade.

⁷⁰ Ninčić, Đ, *Les implications générales juridiques et historiques de la Déclaration d'Helsinki*, Recueil des cours, 154, 1977, pp. 43-102. Ninčić was a Yugoslav diplomat. He received his doctoral degree from the University of Belgrade.

⁷¹ Degan, V., Đ, *Création et disparition de l'État (à la lumière du démembrement de trois fédérations multiethniques en Europe)*, Recueil des cours, 279, 1999.

⁷² Vukas, B, *States, Peoples and Minorities*, Recueil des cours, 231, 1991.

⁷³ The course was delivered in July-August 2023 on Property Rights of Individuals After Changes of Territorial Sovereignty.

⁷⁴ Peace Palace Library search engine, <https://referenceworks-brillonline-com.peacepalace.idm.oclc.org/browse/the-hague-academy-collected-courses>.

⁷⁵ Kolb, *op.cit.*, p. 101.

⁷⁶ Nishitani, *op.cit.*, p. 118.

ures such as R.H. Graveson in 1963, A.A. Ehrenzweig in 1968, W.L.M. Reese in 1976, Cavers in 1980, Juenger in 1983, R.J. Weintraub in 1984, L. Brilmayer in 1995 and Symeonides in 2016 contributed to these discussions. From a civil law perspective, luminaries like G. Kegel in 1964, R. de Nova in 1966, D. J. Evrigenis in 1966, W. Wengler in 1961, H. Batiffol in 1973, Y.E. Lousouarn in 1973, O. Kahn-Feund in 1974, J.F. Lalive in 1977, E. Jayme in 1982, B. Audit in 1984, P. Lagarde in 1986, F. Rigeaux in 1989, F. Visher in 1992, J.D. Gonzalez Campos in 2000, Andreas Bucher in 2010, M. Bogdan in 2011, J. Basedow in 2013, and H. Muir-Watt in 2018, all contributed to these discussions.⁷⁷

Before World War II, some of the notable individuals who addressed general questions included Bartin in 1930 and 1935, Lewald in 1929, 1936, and 1939, Arminjon in 1928 and 1933, Pillet in 1925, Niboyet in 1927, 1932 and 1935) and several others.

Although many professors were invited to teach both a special and a general course, no professor, except for Hans Kelsen (in 1932 and 1953), has been called upon to teach a general course more than once.⁷⁸

Inaugural lectures at The Hague Academy also served as platforms to address significant topics and new developments in Private International Law. One such lecture was presented by Hans van Loon in 2015 on “The Global Horizon of Private International Law”.

For over a decade, the Curatorium has made efforts to include at least one course on arbitration in each session, acknowledging the increasing importance of this subject.

2.5.6. Language

Initially, the courses at The Hague Academy were intended to be taught in French, although the Curatorium had the option to select a different language.⁷⁹ From 1923 to 1939, all lectures at The Hague Academy were conducted exclusively in French.⁸⁰ However, following World War II, in 1947, a course on the International Protection of Human Rights was taught in English by Hersh Lauterpacht.⁸¹ In the same year, B.A. Wortley delivered the first lecture on Private International Law in English.⁸²

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 118.

⁷⁸ Kolb, *op.cit.*, p. 103.

⁷⁹ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 27.

⁸⁰ Nishitani, *op.cit.*, p. 115.

⁸¹ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 55.

⁸² Nishitani, *op.cit.*, p. 116.

2.5.7. Scholarships

In 1924, the Netherlands became the first country to offer scholarships for participants of the Summer Courses at the Hague Academy. In 1926, the Academy itself decided to provide its own scholarships.⁸³

During the existence of the SFRY, many students benefited from the Dutch government scholarships that was granted through the Yugoslav Committee for Cultural Cooperation and International Connections⁸⁴, based on a bilateral treaty on cultural cooperation between Yugoslavia and the Netherlands.

Donations for scholarships have been made possible, and this option has been incorporated into the Academy's statutes, with the specific regulations entrusted to the Curatorium. Today, the Scholarships Regulations are made available on the Academy's website.⁸⁵

In 1998, the Academy received support from thirty-six countries and twenty-one private organisations in the form of donations. It also had 14 individual funds, many of which were established by former members of the Curatorium and former judges of the International Court of Justice. However, following the economic crisis of 2008, the number of donor countries decreased to fourteen.⁸⁶

2.5.8. Yugoslavia in the Centennial publication

In celebration of the jubilee, a publication titled 100th Anniversary has been released. Our region is referenced in four distinct locations within this book:

"On 28 June 1914, the European order collapsed with major consequences for the whole world. On that day, the Austrian heir to the throne, Franz Ferdinand, lost his life in an attack by a Serbian nationalist, after which a chain of political, diplomatic and military procedures was set in motion, which, like a self-sustaining mechanism, quickly led to catastrophe."⁸⁷

"The Permanent Court of Arbitration, which after a very productive start had seen its activities decline in the 1920s and almost out of cases in the first decades after World War II, saw the number of cases explode after 1990. The same was true of the International Court of Justice. The average

⁸³ Joor, *op.cit.*, 67.

⁸⁴ Đorđević, 1968, *op.cit.*, p. 295.

⁸⁵ Scholarship Regulations, <https://www.hagueacademy.nl/scholarship-regulations/>.

⁸⁶ Joor, *op.cit.*, p. 79.

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 28.

annual number of cases the Court of Justice judges dealt with tripled in the period of just over two decades after 1989. In addition to the quantitative change, the cases before the Court also had become very varied, with environmental and human rights issues, topical and at times very complex, such as, for example, the various conflicts linked to the break-up of Yugoslavia.⁸⁸

Speaking of *Recueil des cours*, how the authors were sensible towards important questions, one of the topics mentioned is the succession of States after the dissolution of the former Yugoslavia (“la succession d’États depuis la dissolution de l’ancienne Yougoslavie”).⁸⁹ It is added that certain topics are ostensibly absent, such as the law of armed conflict, despite the war in Bosnia (“malgré la guerre de Bosnie (1992-1995)....”).⁹⁰ Speaking of the crisis that the international law has witnessed during the last hundred years, Professor Yves Daudet, who was Secretary-General of the Academy from 2005 to 2017 and has since then been President of the Curatorium mentioned that there were also violations of the UN Charter, expressly mentioning Kosovo, probably referring to the 1999 aggression against the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (“[i]l y eut aussi, émanant de divers cotes, de violations de la Charte, de natures et degrés variables au Kosovo, en Irak, en Libye ou en Syrie.”).⁹¹

3. Conclusion: Future of The Hague Academy and our Region

The future of the Hague Academy holds both hope and challenges. The expectation is that international law will continue developing and that The Hague Academy will continue its mission for another century.

Professor Yves Daudet outlines the Perspectives of the Academy of Tomorrow. He emphasizes that the Academy’s task is to instil the spirit of universalism among its attendees, while respecting their cultural, historical, political and religious differences. The goal is to prepare individuals who will engage in international dialogue and negotiation at the global level, and this requires an open-minded approach.⁹²

Professor Daudet recognizes a shift in the global balance of power, with Europe on the decline, and Asia’s increasing prominence. This shift has several implications for the Academy. Firstly, orientation towards Asia, Africa and Latin America. In terms of general courses, there is a move from Eurocen-

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 66.

⁸⁹ Kolb, *op.cit.*, p. 96.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*

⁹¹ Daudet, *op.cit.*, p. 190.

⁹² *Ibid.*, p. 192.

trism towards a more global perspective. The Academy should invite professors from these regions to diversify its general course offerings.⁹³ Regarding special courses, there should be a focus on special systems, regional visions or local practices that adapt general international law to specific contexts.⁹⁴ That does not mean abandoning the study of general international law. Secondly, adaptation to new needs: the Academy should remain adaptable and responsive to the evolving needs expressed by professors and attendees, as well as those anticipated by the Curatorium and the Secretary-General. Thirdly, the establishment of “branches” of the Academy in Africa, Asia and Latin America to ensure broader international representation and accessibility.

Overall, The Hague Academy is expected to adapt to changing global dynamics, embrace new topics, and remain a hub for the study of international law while upholding its core values of diversity, dialogue, and the exchange of ideas among a culturally diverse group of participants.

These developments and shifting perspectives imply that scholars of Private International Law from the region, who aspire to be part of and contribute to the work of The Hague Academy will encounter greater competition now, and in the future, compared to their predecessors from former Yugoslavia. The altered geopolitical landscape, coupled with the Balkanization and noticeable orientation of the regional PIL scholarship towards reception and adoption rather than critical and creative contribution, substantially diminishes the likelihood of achieving the remarkable results of Yugoslav jurists, professors and diplomats from the previous century. Regarding student participation, there is an urgent need to institute state and privately funded scholarships that will provide a stable foundation for the continued nurturing of competent international lawyers from the region.

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⁹³ *Ibid.*, p. 193.

⁹⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 194.

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